

New combinations in *Cyperus* (Cyperaceae)

Rajeev Kumar Singh

Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, AIIMS Road, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India

E-mail: rksbsiadsingh@gmail.com; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0136-9243>

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Abstract: One new name and three new combinations are proposed in the genus *Cyperus* L. (Cyperaceae). A lectotype is designated for *Mariscus mayottensis* Cherm. to ensure nomenclatural stability.

Keywords: *Kyllinga mtotomwema*, Lectotype, *Mariscus mayottensis*, *Pycreus richardsiae*, *Pycreus robinsonii*

Introduction

The genus *Cyperus* L. is represented by approximately 955 species worldwide (POWO, 2025). Recent molecular phylogenetic analyses showed that the genera *Kyllinga* Rottb., *Mariscus* Vahl and *Pycreus* P.Beauv. are synonymous with *Cyperus* (Larridon et al., 2014, 2021). Accordingly, one validly published species name in *Kyllinga* (*Kyllinga mtotomwema* Beentje), one in *Mariscus* (*Mariscus mayottensis* Cherm.) and two in *Pycreus* (*Pycreus richardsiae* Vollesen and *P. robinsonii* Vollesen) are here transferred to *Cyperus*. These new combinations reflect the molecular phylogenetic evidence supporting the monophyly of an expanded *Cyperus* that includes *Kyllinga*, *Mariscus* and *Pycreus*. This treatment follows the most recent phylogenomic framework for the Cyperaceae and aligns with current taxonomic practice under the *Cyperus s.l.* concept. Lectotype for the name *Mariscus mayottensis* Cherm. is designated here in accordance with the guidelines and recommendations of Article 9 of the Shenzhen Code (Turland et al., 2018).

New combinations

Cyperus mayottensis (Cherm.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Mariscus mayottensis* Cherm., Notul. Syst. (Paris) 5: 270. 1936.

Lectotype (designated here): Comoros (Union of the Comoros), Anjouan, September 1847, *L.H. Boivin*

s.n. (left hand side specimen of P00196823!).

Remaining syntype: Mayotte (Department of Mayotte), *L.H. Boivin 3062* (right hand side specimen of P00196823!).

Distribution: Comoros and Mayotte.

Notes: Two original specimens of *Mariscus mayottensis* Cherm. are mounted on a single herbarium sheet at P (P00196823). The better-preserved specimen on the left-hand side of the sheet is designated here as the lectotype, as it agrees well with the protologue.

Cyperus mtotomwemae (Beentje) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Kyllinga mtotomwema* Beentje, Fl. Zambes. 14: 322. 2020.

Holotype: Malawi (Republic of Malawi), Nyika plateau, Chelinda bridge, 3 January 1977, *Pawek 12249* (K); isotypes MAL, MO.

Distribution: Malawi and Zambia.

Cyperus richardsiae (Vollesen) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Pycnus richardsiae* Vollesen, Fl. Zambes. 14: 296. 2020.

Holotype: Zambia (Republic of Zambia), Abercorn (Mbala) district, 24 km south of Mbala, Lunzawa, 25 December 1961, *E.A. Robinson 4743* (K001322214!).

Distribution: Endemic to Zambia.

Cyperus vollesenii R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Pycnus robinsonii* Vollesen, Fl. Zambes. 14: 280. 2020.

Holotype: Zambia (Republic of Zambia), Mporokoso district, Mweru Wantipa, Kabwe Plain, 1000 m, 18 December 1960, *H.M. Richards 13751* (K001322215!).

Distribution: Endemic to Zambia.

Etymology: Named after Kaj Børge Vollesen, Danish botanist who worked at the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew.

Notes: The species epithet *robinsonii* is preoccupied in the genus *Cyperus* L. (*C. robinsonii* Podlech, Mitt. Bot. Staatssamml. München 4: 111. 1961), therefore, a new name is herein proposed.

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